

From photons to fish, from seconds to centuries; Generating FAIR data from high resolution sensors in the Western Channel Observatory

D3 – Test Report and Summary of Developed Functionalities

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Constructing Digital Environments
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Executive Summary

The Western Channel Observatory (WCO) is an oceanographic time-series and marine biodiversity reference site that provides a valuable source of data to a wide range of UK research, policymaker, public and businesses communities. Recently, emerging and innovative sensor and platform technologies have proven their abilities to increase both the spatial and time resolution of these data. While this additional data will allow current applications to evolve and improve their capabilities, a new generation of innovative digital solutions such as digital twins or higher level artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) applications require the creation of new, scalable, robust and mature data pipelines that focus on the need to make data truly findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

This mini-demonstrator project has allowed a collaboration among data providers, data users and data archiving centres to investigate and trial approaches to increase the FAIR-ness of marine observation data. From the perspective of data **findability (FAIR)**, this project has implemented intuitive and interactive tools that allow users to find, visualise and explore data and metadata within complex and long-running data series. The developed webpages provide visual, intuitive and interactive toolsets, that allow all data users to search data, interact with enriched metadata, discover and identify data of interest. To improve data **access (FAIR)**, this project has implemented a common interface allows data users to seamlessly access both the British Oceanographic Data Centre's (BODC's) data archive and WCO's near-real time data within a single, intuitive interface. Prototypical tools have been developed within this project that prove the concept of a combined data access ticketing system that guides users through the process of accessing archived and near real-time data through a single, structured and auditable data and metadata access process. To increase data **interoperability (FAIR)**, scientist-centred approaches that encourage the elicitation and use of commonly used community metadata vocabularies that follow FAIR principles have been developed. These approaches focus on the implementation of the UK Marine Environmental Data Information Network (MEDIN) discovery metadata standard, increased use of standardised vocabularies from the NERC vocabulary services improved metadata richness. Approaches to identify and capture data quality via automated quality checking and crowd-sources approaches were also trailed within the developed toolsets, providing a building block towards improved data provenance. Finally, to increase data **reusability (FAIR)**, multi-community approach to enhancing the visibility of metadata and increasing its quality early in the data lifecycle. Data reusability has been enhanced by clarifying and improving the quality of discovery metadata, with an emphasis on increasing the clarity of licencing and open data usage policies.

Focussing on the observatory's CTD (conductivity, temperature, depth) data, this work provides an important step towards enabling a new generation of sensors and platforms to generate scalable, FAIR data sets. In addition, the lessons learned from this development have been shared within a reusable reference architecture framework to provide foundations that allow near real-time environmental data to drive the development of digital twins, machine-to-machine (M2M) data discovery, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) approaches. These foundations are vital to unlocking the potential of data among environmental digital sciences while supporting several NERC Digital Strategy areas, including enhanced data services, facilitating confidence and trust and developing people and skills.

This deliverable (Deliverable D3) is the final output from the WCO CDE mini-demonstrator project, providing a detailed description of the developed capabilities and assessing their performance against the projects aims and objectives in addition to each of the FAIR data principle elements. In addition, a reusable Reference Architecture that describes the toolset's underlying requirements, design decisions and architectural design (Deliverable D2) has been made available to the CDE community [1]. Finally, a demonstration of the toolsets developed by this project were presented at the NERC Digital Gathering 2023 event and are available in written and video formats [2] [3].

Contents

Executive Summary	2
Contents	3
1 Introduction	4
1.1 Document Aim	4
1.2 Aims, Objectives and the FAIR principles	4
1.2.1 Project Aims and Objectives	4
Project Objective 1 – Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualization	4
Project Objective 2 - Ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring	4
1.2.2 FAIR Data Principles	5
2 Test Outputs of the Developed Functionalities	6
2.1 Interactive Data Exploration.....	6
2.2 Enriched Metadata.....	7
2.2.1 Discovery metadata	7
2.2.2 Usage Metadata	8
2.3 Accessing data from multiple sources	9
2.4 Handling of Missing Data.....	14
2.5 Automated Quality Checking	15
2.6 Clarifying licence restrictions and limitations on use	16
2.7 Data User Feedback.....	18
2.8 Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring.....	20
2.9 Downloadable and scientist / human friendly catalogue interface	23
3 Conclusions and Key Project Outputs.....	24
3.1 Analysis of achievements against the aims and objectives.....	24
3.2 Conclusions	25
4 References	26

1 Introduction

1.1 Document Aim

The document, the final deliverable of the Western Channel Observatory (WCO) Constructing Digital Environments (CDE) mini-demonstrator project, provides streamlined test report that details the functionalities developed as part of this project. This document provides an overview of implemented WCO webpage functionalities, including screenshots of the user interface’s webpages, toolsets and sequences developed by this project, before providing a brief description of how the functionalities embody the principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data [4].

The functionalities described within this document are driven by the requirements and architectures described in project deliverable D2 - Requirements and Architecture Document [1]. A demonstration of many of the functionalities described in this document was made as part of the NERC Digital Gathering event in July 2023 (Deliverable D1), a video of which is available to view online [2].

1.2 Aims, Objectives and the FAIR principles

1.2.1 Project Aims and Objectives

The projects aims and objectives were documented in the project proposal [5]. A summary of the aims and objectives are provided in Figure 1 before being described in further detail below. These aims and objectives will be analyzed later in this report to test the completeness of the developments and ensure the mini-demonstrator project has delivered the intended capabilities.

Figure 1 - Project Aims and Objectives

The project aim has been met by focusing on the following objectives:

Project Objective 1 – Make data findable with scalable and tailored data visualization

- External users shall be prompted to select start dates, end dates and variable(s) of interest via embedded widgets to create a visualisation of available data
- External users shall be guided through the data download process, using parameters configured in the drawing regions of the plot
- The visualisation tools should include an intuitive representation of key metadata values (e.g. A traffic light Red, Amber, Green (RAG) representation of data quality values).

Project Objective 2 - Ticketing system to improve data access and impact monitoring

- External users shall be prompted to fill in all details of the request form and submit a data request.
- External users should be prompted to tag any suspected data quality issues against a subset of data.
- The data request form shall auto-populate based on current selections made within the data visualisation tools (Objective 1).
- Data stewards shall be automatically notified, based on the variables of interest that are selected in the form.
- A database shall record requests so impact analyses may be made.

1.2.2 FAIR Data Principles

The project aim focuses on the application of FAIR data principles [4] [6]. A summary of these principles is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Graphical representation of the FAIR data principles

These principles will be referred to throughout the remainder of this document, aligning the activities carried out within this project with the criteria that will maximise the impact of the growing time-series data sets.

2 Test Outputs of the Developed Functionalities

Within this section of the report, screenshots of the functionalities developed within the project are provided along with a description of how that functionality aligns with the FAIR principles or supports the aim of maximising the impact of the WCO's long-term data series.

2.1 Interactive Data Exploration

A key feature of the toolsets developed within this project is the abilities they provide data users to explore the data. Interactive and intuitive toolsets, developed using Bokeh libraries [7], allow users to zoom, pan and select areas of interest within the data. Once the user highlights an area of interest, as shown in Figure 3, the corresponding areas in all linked parameters are also highlighted.

Figure 3 – A screenshot showing a user's subset of selected data across multiple parameters

Although these features do not directly contribute towards the FAIR principles, they align with the project aim of increasing the impact of the data among multiple user groups by allowing users to explore and better understand the content of the WCO's data sets at a glance, encouraging them to access and re-use the most relevant parameters and time periods of interest.

2.2 Enriched Metadata

An important element of increasing the FAIR-ness of data relates to improving the quality of the associated metadata. Within this project, these metadata are considered from two perspectives; discovery metadata and usage metadata.

2.2.1 Discovery metadata

Discovery metadata is a list of information that accompanies data so that users can find out what the data set contains, where and when it was collected and how they can access it. To be used effectively, discovery metadata should align with community standards so that they can be used to catalogue datasets from a range of providers can easily be discovered in widely used, domain relevant data portals and online resources. To support this, the discovery metadata standard selected to be implemented in this project is the one provided by the Marine Environmental Data Information Network (MEDIN) Discovery Metadata Standard [8]. Specifically, MEDIN Discovery Metadata Standard v3.1.2 was selected as a marine community application of the UK government Standard GEMINI2 which, in turn, complies with higher level international standards such as EU INSPIRE and ISO19115. A screenshot showing the visualization of the discovery metadata for the WCO data is provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – A screenshot showing MEDIN discovery metadata located immediately above the parameters of interest.

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 1.

Table 1 – Summarised links between the developed discovery metadata functionality and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Assessment Rationale / Notes
Findable - F2	●	To make data findable, the discovery metadata richly describe the resource. In addition, interoperability is assisted by the use of standards-based vocabularies and the metadata use forms a, shared and community specific format.
Interoperable - I1	●	
Interoperable - I2	●	

2.2.2 Usage Metadata

In contrast to discovery metadata, usage metadata aims to describe the content of the data set with standards-based and community specific parameters and units. A screenshot showing the use of NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) [9] derived parameters within a data exploration pup-up is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – A screenshot showing the presence of NVS-linked parameter labels

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 2.

Table 2 – Summarised links between the developed usage metadata functionality and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Assessment Rationale / Notes
Findable - F2	●	The usage metadata has been assigned to richly describe the resource, including multiple accurate and relevant attributes. In addition, interoperability is supported by the use of standards-based vocabularies and the metadata use forms a, shared and community specific format.
Interoperable - I1	●	
Interoperable - I2	●	
Reusable - R1	●	

2.3 Accessing data from multiple sources

Progress has been made within this project to simplify the process of accessing data from multiple sources. This functionality is of particular importance to a wide range of near-real time data series where data is rapidly acquired into a local staging area before progressing into a data assembly centre (DAC) at a later date. In the case of the WCO, near-real time data is collected from multiple sensors on a regular basis. It typically takes more than 12 months for this data to be packaged up into a complete data set and ingested into the relevant DAC, in this case, the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC). Within this period, a data user may choose to access a time-series that spans data sets held partly within the WCO and partly within BODC.

Use cases like this have been considered within the implementation of the toolsets delivered by this project, providing a simplified and intuitive method that allows users to access the data of interest irrespective of whether it's held entirely within the WCO, BODC or split between the two entities.

An overview of the required process steps and developed functionalities is presented in Figure 6 to Figure 10. In Figure 6, a user can be seen to have highlighted a parameter of interest, a time span or interest and a depth range of interest with the intuitive and interactive toolsets. It may be noted that slices of data can be selected by interacting with the plots directly or by utilising the blue drop-down menus shown at the top of the screen. Once the user has selected the data slice of interest, they can click on the green *Download Composite Data Directly* button shown above the plots.

Figure 6 – A screenshot showing step 1 of the data access process; the user’s selection of a parameter, date range and depth-range of interest.

After clicking on the *Download Composite Data Directly* button, the user is presented with a data ticketing screen and asked to verify their selection of parameters, areas and other information that was automatically populated from their selection. A subset of this information is shown in Figure 7. Once they have confirmed their selections, they can press *Submit* to start an automatic download of the data. It should be noted at this stage that the links between the data visualization and the auto-populated data request page is made entirely via standard, common and open web-protocols, with the page being created from the information contained in a standardised Uniform Resource Locator (URL).

***Site:**

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> L4 Pelagic	<input type="checkbox"/> WCO benthic survey sites	<input type="checkbox"/> Jennycliff	<input type="checkbox"/> Penlee Atmospheric Observatory
<input type="checkbox"/> L4 Atmospheric	<input type="checkbox"/> Whitsand Bay	<input type="checkbox"/> Cawsand	<input type="checkbox"/> PML rooftop
<input type="checkbox"/> L4 Buoy	<input type="checkbox"/> Bigbury Bay	<input type="checkbox"/> E1 Pelagic	<input type="checkbox"/> E1 Atmospheric
<input type="checkbox"/> L4 within 1 km of Buoy	<input type="checkbox"/> Rame shoreline	<input type="checkbox"/> Eddystone	<input type="checkbox"/> river mouths out to L4
<input type="checkbox"/> L4 benthic	<input type="checkbox"/> Plymouth Deep	<input type="checkbox"/> E1 Buoy	
<input type="checkbox"/> L4 benthic at Hilmar's Box	<input type="checkbox"/> Rame	<input type="checkbox"/> L5 Pelagic	

Additional Details

User Notices

- We kindly request that all data uptake is appropriately acknowledged as detailed below:
 - *The Data Policy of the NERC National Capability funded Western Channel Observatory is to make the data freely available at the point of delivery. However, we request that prospective data users first contact the points of contact at PML before obtaining the data. They will provide the metadata, the most up to date versions of the data (where available) and most importantly local expertise in how the data can be used. We expect that co-authorship will be offered to relevant PML experts in response to their active collaboration in projects using these data. Any publication or report using these data should acknowledge them as being provided by the Western Channel Observatory using the following: "The Western Channel Observatory is funded by the UKRI Natural Environment Research Council through its National Capability Long-term Single Centre Science Programme, Climate Linked Atlantic Sector Science, grant number NE/R015953/1"*
- *I have read and agree to The Data Policy
- We would like to contact you in the future to understand how you have used this data.
 - Please tick the box to opt-in
- We would like to include details of your research in some of PML's output such as Reports and Newsletters.
 - Please tick the box to opt-in
- For more information on our privacy practices, and how we are committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, please view our [Privacy Policy](#)
- By clicking submit, you consent to allow Plymouth Marine Laboratory to store and process the personal information submitted above for the sole purpose of providing you with the content requested. Your data request may require us to share your details with The British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) with the sole purpose of providing you with the data that you have requested.

Reset

Submit

Figure 7 - A screenshot showing step 2 of the data access process; the user provides the required information with the WCO ticketing service and presses submit

Once the user has pressed submit, the developed services automatically check the presence of the data within BODC. If data is present within BODC, it is pulled via standard and open web-protocols and compiled into a standard and commonly used .zip file format. In addition, if the data is available in the WCO, that data is also pulled and added to the .zip file. The resulting .zip, containing available BODC and WCO data is downloaded directly to the user's device. The content of the .zip file created by this example request can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8 – A screenshot showing step 3 of the data access process; the relevant files from BODC and/or WCO are downloaded to the user's device

Figure 9 shows the content of the BODC data folder, with data automatically pulled from the DAC and presented in non-proprietary and open .csv data formats. Figure 10 provides a screenshot of the content of this data file, where the relevant data and usage metadata can be found and analysed further on the user's device. This process has completed without the user requiring to know where the data rests, combining data from the WCO's staging area and the DAC to provide a complete, interoperable and reusable data set.

Figure 9 – A screenshot showing step 4 of the data access process; the user has access to all of the data sets selected within the requested date range

Figure 10 – A screenshot showing step 5 of the data access process; The user has directly accessed the data, along with its metadata. from the most appropriate source

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 3.

Table 3 – Summarised links between the developed data access functionality and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Rationale / Notes
Accessible – A1	●	Through this process, the data and metadata have been made retrievable from multiple locations using standardised, open, free and universally implementable protocols. In addition, by using standards-based protocols, the developed functionality provides the ability to add security and authentication as required using commonly applied methodologies.
Accessible – A1.1	●	
Accessible – A1.2	●	

2.4 Handling of Missing Data

The screenshot provided in Figure 11 provides an example of how missing data is handled within the developed functionalities. In this example the Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) data is unexpectedly not present so cannot be plotted. In this case, the plotting service has handled the error gracefully, providing an update to the plot title that clearly explains that no data has been found. Importantly, the discovery metadata for the data set is still made available, in line with FAIR principles.

Figure 11 – A screenshot of a dataset that is unexpectedly missing PAR values.

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 4.

Table 4 – Summarised links between the developed handling of missing data functionality and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Rationale / Notes
Accessible – A2	○	While the discovery metadata are still accessible, even when the data are no longer available, the provenance metadata is not currently updated to reflect this state.

2.5 Automated Quality Checking

The data pipelines developed within this project include architectural elements that encourage the inclusion of automated error checking and reporting. The screenshot provided in Figure 12 shows that, if data fails an automated validation check, the data user is alerted via the use of a red plot background and updated plot title, clearly describing the presence of a validation failure.

While the implemented functionality provides only basic validation tests on the data, checking the data against pre-set upper and lower bounds in addition to checks against a lack of sensor output variance, the presence of this architectural element provides a framework that can be expanded to include more comprehensive tests in future projects. In addition, while the currently functionality alerts data users to data that may contain errors in the developed web-interface, it does not update the related metadata with a report of the test failure. Future work may also be required to identify and implement the reporting of data errors in the metadata through the use of standards-based error reporting flags.

Figure 12 – A screenshot showing red plot backgrounds and updated plot titles, clearly communicating the fact that the data has failed automated validation tests

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 5.

Table 5 – Summarised links between the automated quality checking functionality and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Assessment Rationale / Notes
Reusable - R1	○	This functionality makes progress towards allowing metadata to include attributes that accurately report relevant data quality issues though the use of standards-based error reporting flags. This information is likely to link into the metadata's provenance fields.
Reusable - R1.2	○	

2.6 Clarifying licence restrictions and limitations on use

It's important the any restrictions on the use of the data, or even the absence of restrictions, are clearly documented and communicated to the data user. With out the clear communication of licence terms and limitations, data users will not be able to utilise the data to progress their science. Within the capabilities

developed as part of this project, conditions of data reuse are clarified at two stages; in the discovery metadata and as a separate message when data is requested.

Figure 13 summarises the typical content of the discovery metadata, where details of the licence are communicated in standards-based fields that integrate with external data portals and interfaces, ensuring that the information stays with the data throughout its lifecycle.

In addition, Figure 14 provides a screenshot of functionality that aims to clarify the usage of the data at the request phase. At this stage, the user must use a check box to confirm that they understand the conditions of use, including an example reference format.

Figure 13 – A screenshot showing the highlighting of the discovery metadata’s Limitations on Public Access and Conditions applying to Access and User attributes

Figure 14 – A screenshot of the message displayed to all users when requesting or accessing data.

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 6.

Table 6 – Summarised links between the clarified licence and usage conditions and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Rationale / Notes
Reusable – R1.1	●	Data are released with clear and accessible usage and licence information within the discovery metadata. In addition, human-centric acknowledgement of the terms is prompted when users notify the WCO if their interest in the data,

2.7 Data User Feedback

To monitor the continued maturity of the data sets and their applicability to the community of interest, a lightweight, rapid and intuitive tool has been implemented to collect real-time user feedback. Shown in Figure 15, this tool allows users to select one of three faces; happy, meh (intermediate) or sad. Once selected, the user can optionally add a short comment to provide further information about their rating.

This brief and lightweight interface is primarily designed to encourage feedback from users that do not proceed to data download. The collected feedback is shared with the relevant data stewards within the WCO team for further analysis.

Figure 15 – A screenshot of the developed tools showing the face-based approach to rapidly collecting user feedback

An analysis of how this functionality addresses the FAIR data principles is provided in Table 7.

Table 7 – Summarised links between the developed data user feedback functionality and the FAIR principles

Related FAIR Element(s) [Reference from Figure 2]	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong or complete implementation	Rationale / Notes
Reusable – R1	○	This functionality provides the capability to capture provenance information via a method that is inspired by crowd-source methodologies. While this data is likely to be valuable and will be compiled for human analysis, it does not currently automatically update the associated metadata with pre-defined error flagging parameters.
Reusable – R1.2	○	

2.8 Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring

Once parameters of interest have been identified by the user, they can request access to the data or further information from the associated data steward by completing a data ticketing form.

This data is collected with the primary aim of allowing the WCO teams to gain a better understanding of the data’s impact, allowing better monitoring, reporting and the tailoring of future tools to support key data user communities. The complete set of information requested within the ticketing process is presented in a series of screenshots contained in Figure 16 to Figure 20.

Figure 16 is a screenshot that shows how the user can initiate the process to gain further information about specific data sets from the data’s subject matter experts and data stewards. Specifically, once the user has selected the parameters or date ranges of interest, they can click on the *Custom Data Request Form link*.

Figure 16 – Step 1 of the data ticketing process; the user clicks on one of the multiple Custom data Request Form links (shown in purple)

Once the user clicks on the link, they are taken to a form that elicits information about the user, the project and details of the data request before asking the data user to cite any data used in presentations. The sections of the online form that the user can interact with are show in Figure 17 to Figure 20.

Figure 17 – Step 2a of the data ticketing process; submission of User Details

Project Details

***Project Title:**

Natural Capital Laboratory; Linking social behavior with environmental parameters

Project Type:

- Undergraduate
- Masters
- PhD
- Industry
- Commissioned Project
- Scientific Paper
- Policy Relevant Report
- Other

Project Description:

Postgraduate project investigating the temperature change in Plymouth Sound between 1970-2020 and potential links to human activities in the area

Anticipated Outcome:

- Report
- Thesis
- Conference Proceeding, Journal Paper, Book
- Decision Making Exercise
- Policy Advice
- Other

Figure 18 - Step 2b of the data ticketing process; submission of project details

Data Details

***Start Date:**

01/01/1970

***End Date:**

31/12/2022

***Measurement:**

- Temperature(°C) at Depth (m)
- Salinity(PSU) at Depth (m)
- Density(kgm-3) at Depth (m)
- Transmission at Depth (m)
- PAR (uEm-2s-1) or Turbidity (NTU) at Depth (m)
- Chl a at Depth (m)
- Fluorescence (no unit) at Depth (m)
- Oxygen (uM) at Depth (m)
- Sound Velocity (m/s) at Depth (m)
- Rosette sampler: Depth(m), Temperature(°C), Salinity(PSU), Density(kgm-3), Transmission, PAR (uEm-2s-1) or Turbidity (NTU), Chl a, Fluorescence (no unit), Oxygen (uM),Sound Velocity (m/s)

***Site:**

- L4 Pelagic
- L4 Atmospheric
- L4 Buoy
- L4 within 1 km of Buoy
- L4 benthic
- L4 benthic at Hilmar's Box
- WCO benthic survey sites
- Whitsand Bay
- Bigbury Bay
- Rame shoreline
- Plymouth Deep
- Rame
- Jennycliff
- Cawsand
- E1 Pelagic
- Eddystone
- E1 Buoy
- L5 Pelagic
- Penlee Atmospheric Observatory
- PML rooftop
- E1 Atmospheric
- river mouths out to L4

Additional Details

Figure 19 - Step 2c of the data ticketing process; verification of the data that more information is being requested about

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- *I have read and agree to The Data Policy
- We would like to contact you in the future to understand how you have used this data. Please tick the box to opt-in
- We would like to include details of your research in some of PML's output such as Reports and Newsletters. Please tick the box to opt-in
- For more information on our privacy practices, and how we are committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, please view our [Privacy Policy](#)
- By clicking submit, you consent to allow Plymouth Marine Laboratory to store and process the personal information submitted above for the sole purpose of providing you with the content requested. Your data request may require us to share your details with The British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) with the sole purpose of providing you with the data that you have requested.

About Us

The WCO is a partnership between the [Plymouth Marine Laboratory](#) and the [Marine Biological Association](#).

How are we funded?

The core work of the WCO is funded as part of the UKRI Natural Environment Research Council's National Capability.

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Figure 20 - Step 2d of the data ticketing process; The data request is submitted for further action (Either an automated data download or the notification of the data steward within the WCO)

Although these features do not directly contribute towards the FAIR principles, they align with the project aim of increasing the impact of the data among multiple user groups by providing further information about who is using the data and a greater understanding of how it will be used. This information will be of significant value in future data development activities, as it will allow approaches to be tailored to specific communities of data users

2.9 Downloadable and scientist / human friendly catalogue interface

Throughout this document, progress towards the FAIR data principles has been made because the data are richly described with complete and standards-based metadata. Eliciting this metadata is vital to the creation of FAIR data as, without it, it is of little value in future applications. Similarly, the only current reliable source for this information is the scientific teams that capture the data and design the systems. As such, this project has sought to identify routes to eliciting the information required to create metadata that trade off and optimise the standardisation of attributes and vocabularies along side the need to minimise technical barriers and overheads that would discourage the collection of comprehensive and complete metadata early in the data lifecycle.

This balance has been made through the use of standard, low technological burden tools that scientists already typically use, such as Microsoft Excel [10], coupled with unobtrusive links to standard metadata structures and community vocabularies.

Figure 21 provides a screenshot of a simplified metadata elicitation tool that is based upon a spreadsheet that is already used by the WCO team to capture information about the data. This tool has been modified within this project to better align with the elements mandated by the MEDIN discovery metadata standard as well as linking into standard usage metadata vocabularies, such as those provided by the NVS. By reusing existing tools and processed within the WCO, and in combination with the approach to clearly display metadata compliance throughout the data exploration toolsets, it is anticipated that this linked and embedded approach to metadata elicitation will minimise overheads, drive standardisation and generate FAIR metadata early in the data lifecycle.

Figure 21 – A screenshot of the simple interface to support metadata elicitation

3 Conclusions and Key Project Outputs

3.1 Analysis of achievements against the aims and objectives

The aims and objectives of this project were set in the initial proposal document and are summarised in section 1.2 of this document. This section summarises the work complete and validates the achievements against these aims and objectives.

A summary of the progress made against each of the project's objectives is presented in Table 8.

Table 8 – A summary describing how the implementation has addressed the project objectives

Aim / Objectives		Summary of how the work has addressed the aim/objective	Related document sections
Objective 1	External users shall be prompted to select start dates, end dates and variable(s) of interest via embedded widgets to create a visualisation of available data	The developed interactive and intuitive data exploration tools implement the required features	2.1 - Interactive Data Exploration 2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources
	External users shall be guided through the data download process, using parameters configured in the drawing regions of the plot	User selections in the data exploration toolsets are passed to the download process via standardised and open protocols	2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources 2.8 - Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring
	The visualisation tools should include an intuitive representation of key metadata values (e.g. A traffic light Red, Amber, Green (RAG) representation of data quality values).	Data quality is communicated via colour coded plot backgrounds in addition to updated plot labels	2.5 - Automated Quality Checking
Objective 2	External users shall be prompted to fill in all details of the request form and submit a data request.	The implemented data request form allows impact information to be collected while complying with GDPR guidelines	2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources 2.8 - Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring
	External users should be prompted to tag any suspected data quality issues against a subset of data.	A lightweight approach to feedback allows suspect data to be identified and communicated to subject matter experts	2.7 - Data User Feedback
	The data request form shall auto-populate based on current selections made within the data visualisation tools (<i>Objective 1</i>).	User selections in the data exploration toolsets are passed to the download process via standardised and open protocols	2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources 2.8 - Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring
	Data stewards shall be automatically notified, based on the variables of interest that are selected in the form.	All data request and data feedback forms are integrated with a back-end functionality that prompts the relevant subject matter experts and data stewards when notifications are raised	2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources 2.8 - Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring
	A database shall record requests so impact analyses may be made.	Subject matter experts and data steward prompts are made via an auditable email services, allowing future impact analyses may be made.	2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources 2.7 - Data User Feedback

Aim / Objectives	Summary of how the work has addressed the aim/objective	Related document sections
		2.8 - Data Ticketing – The collection of data for impact monitoring

Finally, the overall aim of the project was to use FAIR data principles to maximise the impact of new, high resolution marine sensing technologies. To assess progress against this aim, Table 9 provides a summary of how each of the project’s activities have progressed towards each of the FAIR principles.

Table 9 - Summarised assessment of the project’s progress against the FAIR data principles

Fair Data Principles	FAIR Element Achieved Progress ○ = progress towards or partial implementation ● = strong progress or complete implementation	Notes / Rationale	Links to relevant evidence within this document.
Findable	●	Improved findability of the data has been achieved by improving metadata visibility and control	2.2.1 - Discovery metadata 2.2.2 - Usage Metadata 2.9 - Downloadable and scientist / human friendly catalogue interface
Accessible	●	This project has trailed innovative approaches that allow users to access data from multiple locations in a transparent and seamless manner.	2.3 - Accessing data from multiple sources 2.4 - Handling of Missing Data
Interoperable	●	Usage and discovery metadata utilises standards-based structures and content.	2.2.1 - Discovery metadata 2.2.2 - Usage Metadata 2.9 - Downloadable and scientist / human friendly catalogue interface
Reusable	●	A focus on improving the clarity of licences and conditions of data use compliment improved metadata to increase the reusability of data in multiple data consuming communities.	2.5 - Automated Quality Checking 2.6 - Clarifying licence restrictions and limitations on use 2.7 - Data User Feedback 2.9 - Downloadable and scientist / human friendly catalogue interface

3.2 Conclusions

Techniques to increase the FAIR-ness of near real-time data have been trailed within this project, with significant advances being made in almost all sub-elements of the FAIR principles across each of the project’s aims and objectives. These improvements will allow the UK’s scientific, policy making and business communities to benefit from the increased spatial and time resolution of near-real time data series, such as those produced by the WCO, during the future deployment of emerging sensor and platform technologies. Supported by learning from the development of a comprehensive set of methodologies and tools, along with the availability of a reusable Reference Architecture developed during this project [1], this high resolution data has the potential to provide real value to digital twins, allowing improved interconnection of observational data with models digital solutions including machine-to-machine (M2M) data transfer, higher level artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms.

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